

BUKHARA (ÖZBEKLER) TEKKESI IN TÜRKIYE

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Abstract. This article describes the role of Bukhara Tekkesi, one of the Uzbek Tekkesi located in the Fatih district of Istanbul, for Turkestanis and its importance in their socio-economic and cultural life

Keywords. Bukhara Tekkesi, Sultan Akhmet, Turkestan, Waqf, dervishes

Bukhara Tekkesi is located in the Fatih district of Istanbul on Sultan Ahmet Square opposite the Sokollu Mehmet Pasha Mosque. Therefore, he was also called Sultan Ahmet Tekkesi. According to the information in the administrative documents stored in the archives of the Main Department of the Waqfs, this building was built in 1692-93. According to an inscription dated October 25, 1900 above the door of the Dargoh Mosque, this mosque and the buildings belonging to it were built by Stambil Bi Gul Kushbeyi, the ruler of the Hissar fortress in Bukhara. According to the inscription above the entrance to the building itself, this khanaka was repaired by Sultan Abdulhamid in 1878-79, because it “was in a state of extreme need of repair.”

Its 3-story building is much larger, but is now in disrepair. It was once much more beautiful and luxurious. It consists of 6 large rooms, a kitchen, a pond, a warehouse, a toilet and several separated rooms for the sheikhs. In the 70s of the 20th century, the wife of the last sheikh and his son lived in this building, and in the large terrace in the courtyard such societies as the “Student Dormitory of Turkestanians” and “Cultural and Social Assistance to the Turkestanians” were located. The building is built of stone. Next to it is a small but very dense cemetery. The stairs lead to the second floor. In the middle there is a courtyard, and around it are cells and a mosque for students. On the third floor, the sheikh and his family, as well as guests, lived in large rooms around a cozy balcony. There was also a vast area, and before the fire there was a harem there. And now this land acts as an internal garden.

In the 70s of the 20th century, the son of the last sheikh, Mehmet Hayreddin, lived in this palace with his family. His father, Sheikh Abudurrahman Buharali, died in 1953. His father was Sheikh Abdulmajid Buharali, whom people called him by adding the adjective “great” to his name. The current existing building was built by this sheikh. His father was Sheikh Yahya, under whom these buildings did not yet exist.

At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, pilgrims from Turkestan stopped at this palace and lived in it for 7-10 days, after which they headed to Mecca. They brought gifts from Turkestan to the sheikh, and he gave blessings to the pilgrims and sent them on the hajj. The sheikh collected gifts and distributed them to those in need. The sheikhs of this palace belonged to the Naqshbandiyya and Rufaiyya tariqats. At the time when this palace was in operation, 2 sheep were slaughtered in it every day: one was consumed by the residents of the palace, and the other was distributed to the poor. On Fridays, people gathered, went to kogitkhan and rested there. The dervishes in the palace were under the protection of the Sultan.

The connections of the palace sheikhs with Bukhara were very close. One day, a group of visitors from Bukhara tried to kill Sheikh Abdurrahman because he was married to a woman from Izmir, and not to a woman from Bukhara. This palace also served as a refuge for refugees from Turkestan for some time. Bukhara tekkesi also ceased to exist in 1925, when all Istanbul tekkes were closed by government decision. In 1945-1950, the Turon association operated here. Currently, the Istanbul Ansor Wakfi Design Center operates in its building.

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